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**JOINT LIABILITY OF COMPANY MEMBERS AND
SHAREHOLDERS FOR COMPANY TAX DEBTS:
INSIGHTS AND LESSONS FROM THE CROATIAN “VEIL
PIERCING” REGIME*****

Abstract: *Comparative experience demonstrates that tax law is an area where companies are not always fully insulated from the liabilities of their members or shareholders, who in some instances may be held personally liable for company’s tax debts. This practice of “veil piercing” in tax matters serves the public interest in ensuring the collection of due taxes. However, it also creates an inherent tension between the legitimate public interest in securing tax revenues and the private interests of company members and shareholders in maintaining limited liability as separate legal persons, thereby avoiding personal responsibility for company tax debts. In modern rule-of-law states, all tax rules are subject to scrutiny through the lens of fundamental rights protections afforded to all potential taxpayers, including third-party debtors. Against this backdrop, this paper explores the limits that legislators must observe when regulating veil piercing in tax matters, with particular attention to the human rights perspective. The analysis is focused on the particular case of Croatian tax legislation, where veil piercing regime has been introduced in 2012.*

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1. Introduction

In modern legal systems, corporations are recognized as having a separate legal personality, distinct from that of their members or shareholders (Pargendler, 2024: 3). One of the most significant consequences of this separateness is the principle of limited liability. Under this fundamental doctrine of modern company law, the company alone is liable itself for its debts with its own assets, while its members or shareholders are protected from personal liability toward the company's creditors (Pargendler, 2024: 8; Elbers, 2016: 324).

A comparative analysis reveals that companies are not always fully insulated from the liabilities of their members or shareholders, who in some instances may be held personally liable for the company's debts (Elbers, 2016: 324). These exceptions to limited liability, employed in various legal contexts, are commonly known as “veil piercing” (Pargendler, 2024: 10). Tax law appears to be an area where the practice of veil piercing is particularly prominent. At the more general level, it has to be noted that comparative tax systems widely incorporate rules imposing various tax obligation on third parties, i.e. persons other than the taxpayer, primarily with the aim to secure tax collection (Baker, Pistone, Perrou, 2023: 86). Instances where company members or shareholders are prescribed joint liability for the company's tax obligations fall within this broader category of tax rules (International Monetary Fund, 2025: 9).

In Croatian tax legislation, a significant turning point can be identified in the 2012 amendment to the General Tax Act¹ (hereinafter: GTA), which introduced the institute of the so-called tax piercing (*proboj pravne osobnosti*). Despite numerous disputes in administrative and judicial practice regarding the application of these statutory provisions, the grounds for the liability of company members for the company's tax debts were expanded in 2024.

Against this backdrop, this paper explores the limits that legislators must observe when regulating veil piercing in tax matters, with particular attention to the human rights perspective. The paper is structured as follows: after this introduction, Section 2 outlines the Croatian legal framework on veil piercing, covering both company law and, in more detail, the GTA provi-

¹ *Opći porezni zakon* (General Tax Act), *Narodne novine*, br. 115/2016, 106/2018, 121/2019, 32/2020, 42/2020, 114/2022, 152/2024.

sions. Section 3 analyses the constraints on designing veil piercing rules from a human rights' standpoint. Just like companies as main taxpayers, third-party debtors are entitled to certain substantive and procedural rights that legislators must respect. The paper concludes with final remarks presented in Section 4.

2. Croatian legal framework of “veil piercing”

2.1. *Veil piercing in company law*

In the Croatian legal order, the basic tenets of corporate separateness are enshrined in the Companies Act of 1993² (hereinafter: CA). The CA endows all registered companies with legal personality. As a general rule, a company alone is responsible for its debts, and this liability is limited to the company's own assets (Article 9 CA). Specifically, for the most common types of companies – limited liability companies (d.o.o.), simple limited liability companies (j.d.o.o.), and joint-stock companies (d.d.), the assets of members or shareholders are protected, except in exceptional cases explicitly defined by law.

However, this benefit of limited liability may be revoked in cases of abuse. Under Article 10 (3) CA, if a company member “abuses the fact” that they are not personally liable for the company's debts, they cannot invoke the protections of limited liability. Furthermore, Article 10 (4) CA outlines four specific scenarios where abuse of limited liability is presumed to exist: (i) using the company to pursue an otherwise prohibited objective; (ii) using the company to cause harm to creditors; (iii) treating the company's assets as personal property; and (iv) reducing the company's assets with knowledge that this could lead to insolvency.

Judicial practice in Croatia reveals that veil-piercing claims are a common litigation strategy against company members. However, success depends heavily on the ability to plead and prove that the member's conduct falls within the aforementioned statutory cases of abuse or their functional equivalents (Marković, 2021: 122, 127). Additionally, court rulings have clarified three key aspects of veil-piercing under the law: (i) the underlying obligation arises from the relationship between the creditor and the company, not from any direct dealings between the creditor and the member; (ii) member liability requires an abuse of the limited liability protection; and (iii) this liabil-

² *Zakon o trgovačkim društvima* (The Companies Act) *Narodne novine*, br. 111/1993, 34/1999, 121/1999, 52/2000, 118/2003, 107/2007, 146/2008, 137/2009, 111/2012, 125/2011, 68/2013, 110/2015, 40/2019, 34/2022, 114/2022, 18/2023, 130/2023, 136/2024.

ity is most accurately understood as a form of joint guarantee concerning the company's debts, allowing creditors to recover from either the company or the member, or both (Marković, 2021: 127).

It has to be noted that, in Croatian company law, the regulation of piercing the corporate veil is deeply influenced by broader private law doctrines. Croatian law of obligations anchors all private-law relationships within a set of general clauses designed to prevent abuse and calibrate the standard of conduct in both performance and the exercise of rights. Central to this framework are the duties of good faith and fair dealing, alongside the prohibition of abuse of rights (see Articles 5–6 of the Civil Obligations Act; hereinafter: COA).³ Supporting these core principles are additional rules addressing damage prevention (Article 8 COA), strict adherence to performance (Article 9 COA), and a measured standard of diligence (Article 10 COA). Against this backdrop, it is evident that the list of abuses outlined in Article 10 of the Companies Act closely reflects the broad anti-abuse provisions found in the COA, as well as the standards of conduct expected in commercial relationships. This alignment ensures that the doctrine of “piercing the corporate veil” is not applied arbitrarily or based on vague notions of fairness, but rather operates as a formalized, codified response to specific instances of bad-faith behaviour in which company assets are wrongfully segregated or shielded from creditors.

2.2 Veil piercing under the General Tax Act

By virtue of the 2012 amendments to the then-applicable version of the GTA, Croatian lawmakers have introduced a targeted regime for veil piercing in the area of tax collection. Similar to approaches in other jurisdictions, this regime functions as a collection mechanism that establishes joint liability for company tax debts not only for company members but also for directors and managers (Baker et al., 2023: 91-92).

The relevant provisions are contained in Articles 29 - 32a of the current GTA. These provisions draw significantly from the veil-piercing regulations found in Croatian company law, with Article 30 GTA essentially replicating the CA rules on limited liability. Crucially, Article 32 GTA establishes that company members generally bear only secondary or subsidiary liability for the company's tax debts. This means tax authorities may initiate enforcement actions against members only if the company itself, as the primary taxpayer, has failed to fulfil its tax obligations (Baker et al., 2023: 92; IMF, 2025: 9).

³ *Zakon o obveznim odnosima* (Civil Obligations Act), *Narodne novine*, br. 35/2005, 41/2008, 125/2011, 78/2015, 29/2018, 126/2021, 114/2022, 156/2022, 145/2023, 155/2023.

Article 31 sets out three situations in which such secondary liability of company members is presumed: (i) depletion of company assets without proper consideration; (ii) conclusion of a sham transaction with an associated person or recognition of a non-existent claim; and (iii) reduction of company assets or concealment of company's financial position contrary to the standard of proper and diligent management, or failure to open the bankruptcy procedure. There is a rebuttable presumption of joint liability for tax debt if any of the circumstances specified in Article 31 GTA are established.

Starting from 1 January 2025, an additional ground for piercing the corporate veil in tax matters has been introduced. According to Article 32a(1) of the GTA, company members can be held liable if the company, as the principal taxpayer, fails to submit the required tax returns within the statutory deadlines. Importantly, in this case, the liability of company members is not subsidiary; they bear joint responsibility for the relevant tax debts (Article 32a(3) GTA), allowing tax authorities to directly initiate enforcement actions against the personal assets of the company members.

From a procedural perspective, this joint liability of company members for company's tax debt has to be established within a special tax proceeding conducted by tax authorities (see Articles 172-177 GTA; Žunić Kovačević, Gadžo, 2013: 653-654).

2.3. Systematic analysis

Since the introduction of veil piercing provisions into the General Tax Act (GTA), Croatian legal scholarship and jurisprudence have sought to interpret their meaning and the criteria for their application, with particular attention to establishing appropriate systemic connections to the more traditional veil piercing framework found in company law legislation.

In this regard, it is important to note that domestic courts rather unambiguously took the stand that the relevant provisions of the GTA did not materially alter the legal positions of company members, shareholders, and directors. The High Administrative Court of the Republic of Croatia (*Visoki upravni sud Republike Hrvatske*), in a series of decisions, has affirmed the existence of a "continuity of liability" for these persons concerning company tax debts; prior to the 2012 amendments to the GTA, liability could be imposed under Article 10 of the CA, and thereafter, liability has been established under the GTA provisions, which essentially mirror those of the CA.⁴ This line of reasoning has also been upheld by the Constitutional Court of the

⁴ See: Gadžo, Žunić Kovačević, 2019: 359-361.

Republic of Croatia (*Ustavni sud Republike Hrvatske*) in a series of rulings in which constitutional complaints filed by company members and directors were dismissed.⁵ This position has been subject to criticism in tax law scholarship, primarily on the grounds that the legal standings of company members and other relevant persons were indeed altered following the 2012 amendments to the GTA. Given that the GTA functions as *lex specialis* in relation to the CA, and considering that the GTA provisions on joint tax liability adopt a *numerus clausus* approach, it is argued that prior to these amendments, company members could not have been held liable for company tax debts solely based on Article 10 of the CA (Gadžo, Žunić Kovačević, 2019: 360-362).

On the other hand, it is beyond dispute that the GTA provisions on veil piercing rely heavily on the terminology and concepts traditionally used in private law and, more specifically, in company law legislation. Brnabić and Ivkošić (2018: 171, 180-184) contend that members of management bodies, who are required under corporate law to exercise the diligence of a prudent and conscientious businessperson, effectively become “tax guarantors” if they fail to fulfil fundamental fiscal obligations such as proper bookkeeping, accurate tax returns, and timely payments. They argue that the illustrative list of veil piercing cases (Articles 31-32 GTA) clarifies circumstances where managerial conduct typically falls short of the requisite standard, thereby justifying personal liability (Brnabić, Ivkošić, 2018: 184). Accordingly, the GTA’s veil piercing provisions must be interpreted against the backdrop of company law diligence standards and the broader private law prohibition on abusive conduct.⁶

It has to be further noted that the GTA places the burden of proof on the tax authority to demonstrate non-diligent conduct that causally impedes tax collection; however, once a specified pattern of conduct is established, statutory presumptions shift the evidentiary burden toward the company member (Brnabić, Ivkošić, 2018: 184, 190). Accordingly, practical application of veil piercing in tax area involves a two-stage test that integrates private law standards, corporate law safeguards, and tax law presumptions. The first stage involves identifying abusive conduct patterns under general legal clauses, such as good faith, abuse of rights, and required standard of care and diligence, alongside the veil-piercing examples set out in Article 10 CA. The second stage requires assessing whether the conduct fits within any enumerated GTA provisions that trigger presumptions of liability for members, managers, and related persons, particularly Articles 31 and 32 GTA. Where

⁵ See: Gadžo, Žunić Kovačević, 2019: 368-370.

⁶ See *supra*, Section 2.1.

both conditions are met, personal liability typically ensues unless the member rebuts the presumption by demonstrating diligent conduct, economic justification, and absence of causal impediment to tax collection (Brnabić, Ivkošić, 2018: 184). This pattern aligns with recent doctrinal analyses emphasizing “good professional” diligence as the relevant standard for corporate managers performing their duties (Slakoper, 2024: 70-71). This standard corresponds with the CA expectation of prudent and conscientious management and complements the GTA’s insistence on efforts towards tax compliance (Brnabić, Ivkošić, 2018: 171, 180-181).

Two important limitations merit emphasis. First, the domain of business judgment, where decisions made in good faith and with adequate information later prove commercially unsuccessful, remains shielded from personal liability. Corporate managers are not guarantors of business success; liability in both company and tax law arises from a lack of diligence or abusive conduct, not mere misfortune (Brnabić, Ivkošić, 2018: 171). Second, the remedies available to creditors under company law and the powers conferred on tax authorities under the GTA are interconnected yet distinct. Crucially, parallel civil and administrative proceedings pursue different objectives: compensation versus public interest in tax collection, and utilize different mechanisms, such as the GTA’s security measures. Nonetheless, coordination rules and the prioritization of tax enforcement actions are justifiable to prevent dissipation of corporate assets (Brnabić, Ivkošić, 2018: 190).

3. Veil piercing in tax area from the human rights perspective: tensions and limitations

As noted in the introductory part of the paper, comparative experiences demonstrate that tax law is an area where veil piercing is particularly prominent. This appears justified, *prima facie*, considering the public interest in ensuring the collection of due taxes, the revenue from which funds a wide range of public goods and services. However, this creates an inherent tension between the legitimate public interest in securing tax revenues and the private interests of company members and shareholders as separate legal persons in maintaining limited liability, thereby avoiding personal responsibility for corporate tax debts (Baker et al., 2023: 86). In modern rule-of-law states, all tax rules are subject to scrutiny through the lens of fundamental rights protections afforded to all potential taxpayers, including third-party debtors. This human rights framework imposes constraints on the design of veil piercing rules, which the legislator must duly observe. The remainder of this Section will examine these safeguards in detail and evaluate the Croatian regime through this normative lens.

3.1. *Veil piercing and the right to property*

As consistently held in the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), taxation is, in principle, an interference with individual's right to peaceful enjoyment of property, enshrined in Article 1 of Protocol No. 1 (hereinafter: Article 1-P1) to the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR).⁷ As with any other interference with property rights, measures in the tax area have to be proportional (in light of the means employed and aims pursued), and do not lead to "excessive burden" upon individual's financial position (Kokott, Pistone, 2022: 461-462). The protection under Article 1-P1 of the ECHR also applies to veil piercing regimes in tax legislation, as collection mechanisms by which joint liability is imposed on persons other than the taxpayer (Elbers, 2016: 324; Baker et al., 2023: 95-96).

It should first be noted that the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has explicitly affirmed in two decisions that veil piercing regimes do not inherently conflict with the property rights guarantees under Article 1-P1 of the ECHR (see ECtHR cases *Klavdianos v. Greece*; and *Khodorkovskiy and Lebedev v. Russian Federation*).⁸ In the *Khodorkovskiy* case, however, the ECtHR found that the Russian veil piercing practice infringed upon the applicants' property rights due to the lack of clarity and precision in the relevant domestic rules, thereby failing the qualitative standards required by the principles of legality and legal certainty (Elbers, 2016: 329). Nonetheless, these requirements of clarity and precision are generally fulfilled by most domestic veil piercing regimes. In case of the Croatian system, under the General Tax Act,⁹ there is no indication that the relevant provisions lack sufficient clarity or precision.

The more challenging issue concerns proportionality (Baker et al., 2023: 98-99): at what point does piercing the corporate veil become an excessive infringement on the property rights of third-party tax debtors? While the ECtHR has yet to clarify the specific factors relevant for the proportionality assessment, some guidance can be inferred from the jurisprudence of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU). The CJEU has, on several occasions, addressed the proper criteria for establishing third-party liability for a company's tax obligations (Baker et al., 2023: 100-101). The first important finding in this regard is that veil-piercing regimes that lead to objective

⁷ See: Baker et al., 2023: 94.

⁸ See: ECtHR, Case *Klavdianos v. Greece*, Application No. 38841/97, 21 September 1999; ECtHR, Case *Khodorkovskiy and Lebedev v. Russian Federation*, Application Nos. 11082/06 and 13772/05, 25 July 2013.

⁹ See *supra*, Section 2.2.

or automated liability of company members, without considering any subjective elements, exceed the limits of proportionality. As noted by the CJEU in the recent VAT case, “(...) the fact that a person other than the person liable to pay the tax acted in good faith, exhibiting all the due diligence of a circum-spect trader, that he or she took every reasonable measure in his or her power and that his or her participation in abuse or fraud is excluded are points to be taken into account in deciding whether that person can be obliged to account for the VAT owed” (C-1/21, *MC v Direktor na Direktsia „Obzhalvane i danachno-osiguritelna praktika“ Veliko Tarnovo pri Tsentralno upravljenie na Natsionalnata agentsia za prihodite*, 13 October 2022, para 76). Put differently, subjective elements should matter in imposing joint liability of company members and other persons for company tax debts (Baker et al., 2023: 100). The second important point is that third-party debtors, including company members and shareholders, should be allowed to escape liability by providing proof that they had nothing whatsoever to do with the acts of the person liable to pay the tax (C-499/10, *Vlaamse Oliemaatschappij*, 21 December 2011, para. 24). Third, it would also be disproportionate to hold a person unconditionally liable for the shortfall in tax caused by acts of a third party over which they have no influence whatsoever (C-499/10, *Vlaamse Oliemaatschappij*, para. 24; C-1/21, MC, para. 74).

Some further interesting insights emanate from the CJEU’s MC decision. In this case, the Court rule that Bulgarian veil piercing regime does not fail the proportionality test. In addition to the elements laid out above, the Court took into account two more elements. First, the Bulgarian regime is limited as regards the extent of a company member or director’s joint liability: they may only be declared liable for the amount by which company’s assets have been depleted as a result of the acts committed in bad faith (C-1/21, MC, para. 82). Second, their liability is incurred only in the alternative, as a subsidiary liability, i.e. where it proves impossible to recover due tax debt from the company itself (C-1/21, MC, para. 83).

It is worthwhile to assess the current Croatian veil-piercing framework, as established in the GTA, in the context of property protection under Article 1-P1, with a particular focus on proportionality. Against this backdrop, there is no indication that the provisions set forth in Articles 29-31 of the GTA disproportionately infringe upon the property rights of third-party debtors. Crucially, the Croatian veil-piercing regime generally incorporates subjective elements when determining the liability of company members, shareholders, and other individuals. As discussed earlier,¹⁰ such liability arises only if their conduct contravenes the principles of good faith, the required stan-

¹⁰ See Sections 2.2 and 2.3.

dards of care and diligence, or is otherwise deemed abusive towards creditors, including the state. Moreover, all potential third-party debtors under the GTA retain the right to prove the absence of liability and rebut the statutory presumptions of abusive behaviour. The proportionality of the regime is further affirmed by the fact that liability is subsidiary, meaning that it can only be imposed if the state has been unable to recover taxes from the company as the primary debtor.

More contentious issues arise with Article 31a of the GTA, which came into force on 1 January 2025. As discussed earlier,¹¹ this provision establishes joint liability for company members if the company, as the principal taxpayer, fails to submit tax returns within the statutory deadlines. In light of the CJEU's findings mentioned above, this new rule appears to impose a disproportionate exposure of joint tax liability on company members. Significantly, the rule does not differentiate between controlling members who influence business decisions of a company and other members who, legally or factually, lack such influence. This resembles the imposition of automatic, objective liability on third-party debtors, which would be likely regarded as disproportionate in light of Article 1-P1 ECHR (Baker et al., 2023: 100). Furthermore, as an exception to the general rule regarding "tax guarantors", Article 31a GTA creates joint and several liability, allowing tax authorities to initiate enforcement proceedings directly against the personal assets of company members. This aspect further supports the conclusion that the provision violates the principle of proportionality.

3.2. Procedural safeguards

Although Article 1-P1 of the ECHR does not explicitly provide procedural guarantees, such protections are implied by its inherent requirement of lawfulness (Baker et al., 2023: 106). The ECtHR has consistently held that any interference with the peaceful enjoyment of possessions must be accompanied by adequate procedural safeguards. These safeguards should provide affected individuals with a reasonable opportunity to present their case to the competent authorities and effectively challenge any measures that infringe upon their rights (Baker et al., 2023: 106; Elbers, 2016: 326).

Procedural rights of third-party debtors in relation to company tax debts stem from various legal sources at the domestic, international, and supranational levels. In the context of Croatia, as well as other EU Member States, particular significance is attributed to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of

¹¹ See Section 2.2.

the European Union (CFR).¹² Article 47 of the CFR guarantees the right to an effective remedy and the right to a fair trial, which also apply within tax procedures. It is important to highlight that procedural safeguards under Article 47 CFR play a vital role across all tax areas governed by EU law, including VAT. Additionally, in several countries, including Croatia, these procedural rights are enshrined at the constitutional level. For example, Article 29(1) of the Constitution of the Republic of Croatia¹³ extends fair trial rights to both administrative and judicial stages of tax proceedings.

Among the fundamental procedural guarantees available to taxpayers and third-party debtors under these legal frameworks is the right to be heard. Given that tax authorities may adversely impact the legal interests of third-party debtors, these individuals must be afforded the opportunity to present arguments in their defence and contest claims brought by tax authorities (Kokott, Pistone, 2022: 226). Other essential procedural safeguards include the right to judicial protection and access to documents (*habeas data*) (Kokott, Pistone, 2022: 206-207).

Turning back to the Croatian veil piercing regime, it is clear that company members and shareholders as potential third-party debtors have the right to judicial protection. When joint tax liability for company tax debt is imposed on any of them, they first have the right to seek an administrative review and subsequently to appeal before administrative courts (Rožac, 2021: 406). Additionally, administrative provisions in Articles 172-177 of the GTA *prima facie* provide sufficient safeguards regarding third-party debtors' rights to be heard and access relevant documents. In sum, third-party debtors have an opportunity to present their case before tax authorities and courts, arguing that the requirements for establishing their joint tax liability have not been satisfied.

Nevertheless, the Croatian veil-piercing framework exemplifies a fundamental structural issue concerning the procedural rights of third-party debtors. Specifically, these procedural safeguards are limited to a special proceeding that determines joint liability, which is only initiated after the primary tax proceedings (where the company's tax debt as the main taxpayer is established) have been finalized. As noted in relevant literature, "if the company that has been assessed with the tax has not contested the assessments, the individual who is jointly and severally liable may lack the opportunity to

¹² Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, *Official Journal of the EU*, no. C 202/389, 7.6.2016.

¹³ The Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, *Official Gazette* Nos. 56/90, 135/97, 113/00, 28/01, 76/10, 5/14.

challenge the assessments on substantive grounds” (Baker et al., 2023: 107). The relevant provisions of the Croatian GAT do not offer adequate procedural protections to company members in this regard.

A recent case from the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) concerning the Polish veil-piercing regime (C-277/24, *M.B. v Dyrektor Izby Administracji Skarbowej we Wrocławiu*, 27 February 2025) illustrates this problem clearly. In that case, M.B., who was the chairperson of the management board of the company B. sp z o.o., filed a complaint alleging that the Polish tax authorities had denied her status as a party to the tax proceedings against the company. The tax authorities argued that M.B. lacked a legal interest in participating in the company’s tax proceedings, despite the fact that under Polish law she could be held jointly liable for the company’s tax debt. The authorities maintained that a third-party debtor could only be recognized as a party in the specific joint and several liability proceedings. Analysing the case-matter primarily from the perspective of third-party debtors’ rights of defence, the CJEU has come to the following conclusions (C-277/24, M.B., paras. 59-65): (i) national legislation and practice may deny a third party, who may be held jointly and severally liable for the tax debt of a legal person, the status of a party to the tax proceedings brought against that legal person to establish the tax debt of that legal person; (ii) however, that third party, during any joint and several liability proceedings brought against that third party, should be able effectively to call into question the findings of fact and the legal classifications made by the tax authority in the context of the (main) tax proceedings, and to have access to the file of the tax authority, in accordance with the rights of that person or of other third parties.

4. Conclusion

The Croatian tax legislation exemplifies how the doctrine of corporate separateness has significant limitations in the tax law domain. Under the Croatian General Tax Act (GTA), company members and shareholders can be held liable for the company’s tax debts. The GTA’s veil piercing provisions draw inspiration from more general veil piercing rules found in Croatian company law. Consequently, the practical application of veil piercing in tax matters in Croatia follows a two-stage test that integrates private law standards, corporate law safeguards, and tax law presumptions. Importantly, the GTA’s veil piercing rules must be interpreted considering company law standards of diligence and the broader private law prohibition against abusive conduct.

This paper has analyzed the Croatian veil piercing regime from a systemic perspective, focusing on fundamental rights protections afforded to all potential taxpayers, including third-party debtors. Substantively, any veil piercing regime must comply with property rights protections under Article 1-P1 of the ECHR, with particular emphasis on proportionality. Procedurally, company members and other third-party debtors should have the right to be heard, access judicial protection, and obtain relevant documents. The CJEU case law, particularly the recent decision in M.B. (C-277/24) provides valuable guidance on balancing the public interest in tax collection with taxpayers' fundamental rights.

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Case law

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**ЗАЈЕДНИЧКА ОДГОВОРНОСТ ЧЛАНОВА ДРУШТВА И АКЦИОНАРА ЗА
ПОРЕСКЕ ДУГОВЕ ДРУШТВА: УВИДИ И ЛЕКЦИЈЕ НА ПРИМЕРУ
ХРВАТског РЕЖИМА „ПРОБОЈА КОРПОРАТИВНОГ ВЕЛА“**

Резиме

Упоредно искуство показује да пореско право није област у којој су друштва увек у потпуности заштићена од одговорности својих чланова или акционара, који се у неким случајевима могу сматрати лично одговорним за пореске дугове друштва. Ова пракса „пробоја вела“ у пореским стварима служи јавном интересу у обезбеђивању наплате пореских обавеза. Међутим, она такође ствара урођени сукоб између легитимног јавног интереса у обезбеђивању пореских прихода и приватних интереса чланова друштва и акционара у одржавању ограничене одговорности као засебних правних лица, чиме се избегава лична одговорност за пореске дугове друштва. У савременим државама правне државе, сви порески прописи подложни су преиспитивању кроз призму заштите основних права која се пружају свим потенцијалним пореским обавезницима, укључујући и пореске јемце. У том контексту, овај рад испитује границе које законодавац мора поштовати приликом регулисања „пробијања правне личности“ у пореским питањима, са посебним освртом на заштиту људских права. Анализа је фокусирана на посебан случај хрватског пореског законодавства, где је режим „пробоја вела“ уведен 2012. године.

Кључне речи: пореско право, пробој корпоративног вела, заједничка одговорност за порески дуг, права пореских обавезника.

